

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6628998

BREATHING OF AN ACTIVE OR A PASSIVE SMOKER ATHLETE AND TOBACCO SMOKE

Giorgi Parulava - Professor, Doctor of biological sciences (paru56@mail.ru);
Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia.

David Zurabashvili - Professor, Doctor of medical sciences;
Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Elene Parulava - Master; Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences, Germany.

Nana Gelenava - Associate Professor, Academic Doctor;
Zugdidi Shota Meskhia Teaching University, Georgia.

Enver Arveladze - Associate Professor, Academic Doctor;
Zugdidi Shota Meskhia Teaching University, Georgia.

Abstract. Breathing is especially important in active and passive smoking athletes. Our research confirms that the widespread belief in society that the negative effects of tobacco smoke on the respiratory tract are neutralized by constant exercise is false. We confirm that inhalation of tobacco smoke alters metabolism at the cellular level, impairs muscle protein synthesis, and activates a gene that causes a decrease in muscle mass. Decreased functional capacity of the lungs, especially as a result of the deposition of dense particles of tobacco smoke in its lower parts, disrupts the rhythm of respiration (inhalation, exhalation), increases the pressure on both the lungs and the entire cardiovascular system. The data are presented and the main part of the composition of toxic substances in cigarette smoke and their toxicity rate are determined. Also, to what extent does the maximum amount of harmful substances exceed the generally accepted norms in terms of volume or mass, which does not cause painful changes in the body and hereditary changes in the offspring for an indefinite period of time, but significantly worsens and degrades the athlete's performance.

Keywords: Tobacco smoke, Toxic substances, Metabolism, Respiration, Smoker, Athlete.

Introduction

Issues of passive smoking are especially important in the aspect of sports activities. At present, the widely held opinion that regular exercise can neutralize the harmful effects of tobacco smoke on a person is completely refuted. New directions and methodological approaches to the study of the problem of passive smoking in sports medical, sports psychological, sports social and other sciences about a person engaged in sports activities are being developed. It is well known that smoking is harmful to health. Scientific studies show that not only regular smoking, but also passive smoking changes metabolism at the cellular level, impairs muscle protein synthesis processes and increases the activity of genes that cause sarcopenia - age-related muscle loss. There is a significant imbalance in the athlete's hormonal system: the level of stress hormones (mainly cortisol) rises sharply, the level of testosterone and a number of other hormones important for maintaining muscle mass gradually decreases. Even passive smoking negatively affects strength training, prolonged exposure to tobacco smoke exacerbates this harm [1; 2].

The growth of the athlete's muscle mass is also directly related to oxygen metabolism, the violation of which in the body is always observed with passive smoking. The most harmful for the development of human muscle mass is considered to be carbon monoxide (carbon monoxide),

which significantly prevails in tobacco smoke. When tobacco smoke is inhaled, it binds to the haemoglobin of red blood cells, disrupting their ability to carry oxygen, which negatively affects the recovery processes in muscles after strength exercises, and in total can be expressed in a decrease in strength indicators and increased fatigue.

Since the lungs and the respiratory system function less efficiently (a decrease in the functional volume of the lungs as a result of the accumulation of solid particles of tobacco smoke deposited in the lungs in the amount of up to 70%) [2; 7], the rhythm of breathing (inhalation, exhalation) is disturbed and the load on both the lungs and the heart increases. the vascular system of a passive smoker. Both active and passive smokers change their breathing rhythm. It becomes more superficial and quickened, the chest loses the necessary mobility, pulmonary ventilation decreases. As a result, the system of muscles involved in the breathing process gradually weakens, endurance and the ability to engage in sports activities at full strength decrease. Passive smoking, otherwise inhaling tobacco smoke at a certain distance from an active smoker, has an "accumulator effect"[5].

Aim and Objectives

In the proposed chapter, the article provides relevant data on individual issues of structure, analysis, patterns of influence, and the success of the adaptation of a passive smoker in conditions of increased need for the breathing process, in other words, in conditions of sports activity. It will also set how many times the content of the substance in tobacco smoke exceeds the value of the maximum permissible concentration.

Materials and Methods

Tobacco smoke in its structure is an aerosol containing vapour and micro particles. Although nicotine is most often measured as a major component in the determination of the structure of the vapour phase of tobacco smoke, it is not an ideal marker, due to its unpredictable rate and not fully understood decomposition pathways (photochemical processes in the surrounding atmosphere), as well as its high adsorption properties [5]. The method of qualitative and quantitative identification of tobacco smoke components is quite complicated, because sampling and determination of concentrations of suspended particles depends mainly on the nature and conditions of ventilation of closed and open spaces [2]. Air sampling to determine the components of tobacco smoke in it is most often carried out by the aspiration method, based on pulling a specific volume of air through the absorption system. Thus, at present, biological monitoring is of particular relevance, aimed at the qualitative and quantitative identification of air pollutants and subsequent control of the leading components selected, based on biochemical indicators [4; 11].

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of nicotine, benzene, propyl benzene, toluene, xylene, phenol, styrene, isoprene, formic and acetic acids in tobacco smoke was carried out in the most securely closed room with a volume of 36.0 m³.

Cigarettes with the following technological parameters were used: cigarette length 70.0 ± 0.5 mm; cigarette tape width 28.0 ± 2.0 mm; fiber width 0.7 mm with tolerances, respectively, not higher than 20.0%. In the proposed work, we do not provide brands and technologies for the production of tobacco products, as well as the botanical origin and grade of raw materials. In a smoking machine, as a standard, products were smoked that were strictly uniform in terms of the place of manufacture (factory, production line, machine tools, etc.) and the nature of storage.

According to standard requirements, the characteristics of tissue paper, sizing, filters, dyes, clichés were the same as possible.

The distal part of the tobacco product was separated with a razor, weighed (2.0 GR) and, together with the rim paper, was placed in the pyrolyzer drum. The hole was hermetically sealed. As soon as the drum temperature of the smoking machine reached 600[deg.]C, the hole opened on its own and tobacco smoke entered the atmosphere of the room. The studies were carried out at three different room temperatures:

- cold air, but not frost (3.0-5.0°C)
- comfortable ambient temperature (18-20°C)
- the maximum allowable temperature for an enclosed space (38-40°C)

The analysis of cigarette smoke was carried out at distances of one, two, three, four, five, six, seven, eight and nine meters from the smoking machine in the following sequence: after 10.0 minutes; 20.0 minutes; 50.0 minutes; 100.0 minutes and 150.0 minutes after the start of the experiment (opening the pyrolyzer lid). The experiments were carried out three times for each zone and were processed accordingly. In order to eliminate residual concentrations of cigarette smoke products, an interval of 15 days was carried out between each experiment. At the same time, before the start of each experiment, a chromatographic analysis of air was carried out to exclude background pollution.

The method of "point selection" was used, which makes it possible to study the composition of the air environment by chromatography methods at specific distances from the smoking machine at a fixed time (according to a given program). The sample probe (4 at each point) was placed in such a way as to completely exclude mutual overlap of air samples. The reverse exhaust was extinguished by a special filter.

In our studies, the matrix has an organic (hair, saliva, blood plasma, sweat) and inorganic nature (air, main and side cigarette smoke). The assessment of the significance of each matrix was carried out according to the chromatographic method. Gas-liquid chromatography is a highly developed, extremely sensitive and long-standing method of analytical chemistry. Approximately more than 50% of the work on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of trace levels of organic substances is based on the application of this methodological approach.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the components of tobacco smoke is given by adsorption gas-liquid chromatography on a gas chromatograph PPF-Milliporwaters (USA). A quartz capillary column 120.0 meters long and 0.35 mm in diameter was used. The walls of the capillary are covered with a stationary liquid phase 0V-101. Coating thickness 5.0 microns. Carrier gas flow rate (helium) - 3.0 ml/min. Retention value 20.800 theoretical plates (for benzene). The principle of temperature programming is used. After the injection of the sample, the isothermal mode (20°C) was maintained for 8.0 minutes. Next came programming with a step of 2.0 g/min up to a maximum temperature of 200.0°C, and then the isothermal mode was maintained. Evaporator temperature 240.0°C, detector temperature 260°C.

Flame ionization detector. Discharge to atmosphere up to 80.0%. The so-called "support" method was applied, which is based on the supply of gas to the detector through a specialized fitting (bypass line) in a volume of 20.0 ml/min. Dosing was done with a Hamilton-N6 microsyringe. The area of each chromatographic peak was calculated using the corrected retention time on a Model 730 integrator, Data-Module (Waters). Program M. The spread of concentrations determined in cigarette smoke of substances was covered by a combination of several independent chromatographic channels (pair inclusion), which made it possible to carry out a fairly reliable assessment (scatter no more than 2.0%) both in the upper and lower (trace

volumes) concentrations. In all cases, the probability of sorption of substances in gas communications (mirror values of the electrical response) was taken into account.

In order to optimize the analysis process: retention rate, selectivity, number of theoretical plates, the following regulatory factors were applied: separation selectivity, which was determined by comparing the retention rate of two peaks (retention time and volume and separation modes), which were determined by the strength of the solvent (eluting power), the nature of the packing and the volume of the column.

It is known that the number of theoretical plates serves as a measure of the width of the peaks in a particular chromatographic system [5] It is proportional to the square of the ratio of retention volume to peak width. The resolution equation is as follows:

$$R = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{a-1}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{K^2}{1+K^2} \right) (N) \left(\frac{K^1}{1+K^1} \right)$$

selectivity efficiency capacitance

where R is the resolution of the chromatographic column, K^1 is the degree of retention, and is the selectivity or the ratio of the degrees of retention of the two peaks of interest to us (K^2/K^1) N is the number of theoretical plates.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of nicotine in the air includes the following steps: concentration from the air with a specially prepared adsorbent, extraction with diethyl ether, evaporation to organic oil, re-extraction with ethanol, gas chromatographic separation on a capillary column and quantitative determination.

The concentration of nicotine in the atmospheric air (mg/m^3) is calculated according to the formula [2]:

$$C = \frac{m}{V_0}$$

M is the mass of nicotine, according to the calibration characteristic.

V is the volume of air taken for analysis and reduced to normal conditions.

C - measurement results.

The confidence error of measurement should not exceed 23% at a confidence level of 0.95. We consider it necessary to provide quality control indicators for the reproducibility of fixed retention times (\pm minutes) of our chromatographic analysis.

Research Results

It is shown that athletes and untrained individuals have a multidirectional reaction of the respiratory system to physical activity. Athletes after physical work have a significant increase in vital capacity and expiratory reserve volume, while in untrained individuals, the vital capacity of the lungs after exercise does not change, and the increase in expiratory reserve volume is accompanied by an adequate decrease in inspiratory reserve volume. After exercise, athletes have a decrease in the airflow rate at the level of large bronchi, which is compensated by an increase in bronchial patency at the level of medium and small bronchi. The latter is provided primarily

by the effort of the respiratory muscles. In trained individuals, bronchospastic reactions during physical activity were not detected, the air flow rate increases at all levels of the bronchial tree.

These issues are of particular importance among people with constantly high physical activity. First of all, this concerns the nature of sports activities and sports that require targeted high pulmonary ventilation during regular training. The total surface of the walls of the pulmonary alveoli with a deep breath at the time of maximum physical activity increases to hundreds of square meters. The growth of pulmonary ventilation occurs not only due to the respiratory rate, but also as a result of the inclusion of additional volumes (lung reserve) in the process of enhanced gas exchange. At rest, the anatomical dead space corresponds to the functional dead space and is about one third of the tidal volume.

The adaptive capabilities of the pulmonary system, the external respiratory apparatus are very large. This ensures that the optimal gas state of the blood is maintained during exercise.

It is interesting to cite some figures that highlight the toxic effects of tobacco smoke at the level of not only active, but also passive smokers:

- smoking 20 cigarettes per day, the smoker receives 500 x-rays of exposure per year;
- 25% die prematurely from the effects of smoking;
- 7 seconds is required for the penetration of nicotine into the brain by inhalation of primary and secondary tobacco smoke;
- 90% of lung cancer causes are active smoking;
- more than 4,000 different chemicals are contained in tobacco smoke (main and secondary), in addition, modern studies show that there are much more toxic substances in secondary tobacco smoke;
- Carcinogenic components of tobacco smoke are in the body for 70 hours during passive smoking;
- 2 hours of passive smoking is equivalent to smoking one cigarette;
- about 6,000,000 people die every year from smoking-related causes, of which more than 3,000 die from second-hand smoke from lung cancer;
- the influence of nicotine is especially pronounced in children and adolescents;
- children lag behind in mental and physical development;
- the level and nature of intraschool adaptation is sharply violated. Children do not study well, violate intra-school discipline;
- it is generally accepted that many smokers have a history of schizophrenia;
- a side effect of smoking appears in the form of a headache; insomnia often develops.

The identification of each component of tobacco smoke at different periods and at different distances from an active smoker gives an idea of the level of real danger that a passive smoker is exposed to. When assessing the real danger, it is necessary to take into account, first of all, the form and duration of the passive smoker's stay in an atmosphere polluted with tobacco smoke. Depending on the environmental parameters (air temperature, lighting, humidity), the nicotine contained in both streams of tobacco smoke is monoprotonated differently and is not equally formed in the form of particles easily transported by air streams.

Below are tables where the most important toxic substances present in tobacco smoke are rewritten.

Composition and toxicity of tobacco smoke

The toxicity index indicates how many times the content of a substance in tobacco smoke exceeds the value of the maximum permissible concentrations.

The list of substances given in the table is given according to their share in the total toxicity.

Discussion. The exchange of gases between cells and the environment is commonly called respiration, which is divided into the following four stages:

- exchange of gases between the air and lungs;
- exchange of gases between lungs and blood; - transportation of gases by blood; - gas exchange in tissues.

The first part of gas exchange is performed by the respiratory system. The circulatory system performs the rest of this process. It is customary to talk about pulmonary respiration, which provides gas exchange between air, blood and tissue respiration, which performs gas exchange between blood and tissue cells. There is a close relationship between lung and tissue respiration [2; 3].

Muscular activity is the main factor influencing the functioning of the respiratory system, because there is a close physiological and functional relationship between the apparatus of movement and the respiratory system. Each movement, causing a change in the chemistry of the muscles, reflexively and humorally excites the function of respiration. The term "respiratory failure" refers to the state when normal breathing at rest, or increased breathing, adequate to physical activity, is not able to provide the required saturation of arterial blood with oxygen. Arterial hypoxemia sets in. The main way to compensate for respiratory failure is shortness of breath [9; 12].

Respiratory movements of the chest are caused by contraction and relaxation of not only the respiratory muscles of the diaphragm and intercartilaginous and intercostal formations, but also the so-called "special respiratory muscles". In the process of sports training, when the depth of breathing reaches 30-40% of the vital capacity of the lungs, additional muscles are usually included. Many muscle groups of the neck, chest, back and abdominal cavity with very deep breathing have a dual function: participation in motor activity and participation in breathing at

the expense of skeletal muscles intended for motor activity, which significantly impoverishes the process of sports training.

For all types of sports muscle activity, there are no identical recommendations for optimal breathing. The body has a reaction of expediency that enters the respiratory center of information, which independently optimizes the breathing process. The specifics of sports activity, rhythm, nature of movements, their intensity and duration, as well as ambient temperature, barometric data and many other factors undoubtedly affect the nature of breathing. According to existing special studies, rare, but very deep breathing (frequency 20-30 times per minute, depth 70-85% of vital capacity) is not effective enough [10; 11]. During strenuous physical work, the highest oxygen consumption occurs when breathing at a frequency of 40-85 times per minute and a depth of 35-60% vital capacity of the lungs.

With professional sports activities and high fitness, a condition can occur that is described as a "feeling of euphoria, or a second wind." The effect of a second breath can be created as a result of prolonged physical activity of an aerobic nature. Along with this, it is generally accepted that a second wind usually does not appear in well-trained athletes. With a high level of professionalism, the work of the chosen power is performed by a well-trained athlete for as long as he has enough energy reserves (glucose, glycogen, fats) [8]. The second wind effect is a balance between the production and consumption of acidification products resulting from exercise. In the process of physical exercise, the optimization of the respiratory rhythm and depth is no less important than the physical work done.

The intake of tobacco smoke into the human respiratory system adversely affects the process of oxygen uptake by the body, and thus disrupts the most important physiological process - breathing. Alveolar capillaries, instead of being enriched with oxygen, are saturated with carbon monoxide, which combines with haemoglobin to form carboxyhemoglobin. As a result of this process, a significant part of haemoglobin does not take part in the supply of oxygen to the body. In heavy smokers who inhale more than 800 g of suspended particles of tobacco tar during the year, about 1.0% of lung tissue is excluded from the breathing process per year. Deep, poorly ventilated areas of the lungs tend to accumulate carcinogenic components of tobacco tar. Tobacco smoke acids (butyric, propionic, acetic, and others) easily dissolve carcinogens deposited in poorly ventilated pulmonary lobes, which, when they enter the bloodstream, spread throughout the body, causing cancers of the respiratory tract, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, and genitourinary system.

When smoking, two streams of tobacco smoke are formed: main and side. When puffed, the main stream of tobacco smoke is formed, which enters the smoker's body only as a result of movement along the cigarette column.

As a result of intense smoldering of the distal end of the cigarette, between puffs there is a side stream of cigarette smoke that enters the external environment (about 2/3 of the smoke from a burnt cigarette), polluting it with nicotine, tar and many other products of pyrolysis and photosynthesis of tobacco smoke components.

Tobacco smoke enters the lungs of both heavy smokers and passive smokers in the immediate vicinity. As a result of lowering the "freshness index" on a passive smoker, the direct toxicity of the air environment and the indirect toxicity resulting from smoking act in combination.

It is believed that when smoking three cigarettes in a closed space of 35.0 square meters and a volume of about one hundred and fifty cubic meters, the amount of light ions responsible for the value of the "freshness index" decreases by 68%.

Environmental problems, primarily issues of air pollution by toxic components of tobacco smoke, are important in the life of people who have devoted themselves to sports activities [6;10]. Health, physical capabilities of not only active, but also passive smokers are closely related both to the toxic components of the main and side tobacco smoke, and to the characteristics of pulmonary ventilation, which largely changes during physical exertion of different duration (types of athletics) and varying degrees of intensity (weightlifting programs). The supply of oxygen to the body, the lungs-blood participation, gas exchange processes (the so-called external respiration) are provided by various physiological mechanisms that are fundamentally different for most sports disciplines: pulmonary ventilation, diffusion through the alveolar-capillary membranes, the intensity of pulmonary blood flow, the depth and nature of breathing (inhale, exhale). These processes are interconnected.

In the process of inhalation, not all the air entering the respiratory system undergoes gas exchange. A certain part of it remains in the so-called "dead space". This space is approximately a few tens of percent of the respiratory lung volume and anatomically (normally) corresponds to the physiological [11; 12]. The ratio of these volumes contributes to the optimal saturation of arterial blood with oxygen. In this process, the oxygen capacity of the blood, the state of its acidity, the partial pressure gradient and many other factors are important.

Findings

Pulmonary respiration is exclusively influenced by the tar present in tobacco smoke. Not only in active smokers, but also in passive smokers, the tar of tobacco smoke settles and accumulates in poorly ventilated sections of the lung tissue, in the alveoli of the "dead space". The adaptive capabilities of the external respiration apparatus are exceptionally large and can actually increase in the course of appropriate sports and training activities, and are able to correspond to the actual physical load of the intensity required during this period.

Despite the obvious conclusion that even a small amount of tobacco smoke (passive smoking) is incompatible with sports, this issue remains not fully recognized both among representatives of professional sports activities and among people who are not interested in a sports career.

Oxygen exchange occurs most efficiently in the lower parts of the lungs. The so-called deep-diaphragmatic (abdominal) type of breathing: an indicator of the "royal posture" of the chest and spine.

Correct breathing is considered nasal. Breathing through the mouth limits the vital capacity of the lungs, reduces the intensity of gas exchange. Nasal breathing activates the diaphragm as much as possible, just as meditation calms the biorhythms of the brain, activates its Alpha rhythm. With an increase in physical activity, the transition to oral breathing occurs automatically. Physiologically, inhalation is slightly shorter than exhalation. The fuller the exhalation, the deeper the inhalation becomes, and the ventilation of the lungs increases. During strength exercises, it is recommended to exhale at the moment of the greatest muscle effort, and inhale at the moment of the least. However, for each sports discipline there is a strictly defined rhythm and depth of breathing, which must be observed even in the absence of sports qualifications. The muscles with which we inhale and exhale, according to most experts in sports activities, are an indispensable part of the main stabilizing and postural control system.

References

1. გელენავა ნანა. თამბაქოს ბოლი და მისი პიროლიზი. თბილისი, 2009, 125 გვ.

2. Зурабашвили Д. З., Парулава Г. К., Пассивный курильщик, вопросы медицины спорта. Тбилиси, 2019, 295 ст.
3. Зурабашвили Д. З., Парулава Г. К. Уровень никотина и котинина в слюне пассивных курильщиков. International academy Journal? Web of Sclar. 2(20), vol. 1. February 2018: 86-91. Poland.
4. Зурабашвили Д. З., Парулава Г. К. Уровень никотина и котинина в волосах пассивных курильщиков. International academy Journal Web of Sclar.
5. Зурабашвили Д.З., Чантурия Н.Р., Капанадзе Л.Р. Хроматографический анализ отдельных токсических компонентов конденсата табачного дыма биологических тканях. Мед. Новости Грузии.
6. Zurabashvili D., Parulava G., Gvishiani Z., Shanidze L., Garuchava M., The level of Naphthalene and its Derivates in Tobacco Smoke, Georgian Medical News, 2016:1 (250): 93-97, Tbilisi.
7. The Social Climate of Tobacco Control Web Site. Available at: www.socialclimate.org, Accessed June 30, 2013 (Continued from first pa).
8. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Harmful and potentially harmful consistent in tobacco products and tobacco smoke; Established list. Fed. Regist. 2012; 74(64):20034-20037.
9. Zurabashvili D., Chanturia J., Kapanadze L., Danelia G. The influence of Tobacco-smoke components on Ketopropionic Acid concentration in Tooth of tobacco-smokers. Georgian Medical News. N2(179)2010: 27-31.
10. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services: The Health Benefit of Smoking Cessation: A report of the Surgeon General, 2009.
11. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services: The Health Consequences of Involuntary Exposure in Tobacco Smoke: A Report of the Surgeon General. 2006, Atlanta G.A.
12. Zurabashvili D., Gvishiani Z., Influence of Environmental Temperature on the Migration of Different Components of Tobacco Smoke. Bul. Of the Georgian Academy of Science; 2005;171; N3:102-106.